

THEOLOGICAL MOTIFS IN PSALM 23 AND ITS IMPLICATIONS FOR HUMAN INSECURITY IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to examine the theological motifs in Psalm 23 with a view to applying them to the security challenges in Nigeria, using the psalm as a basis for proposing solutions to the menace. To achieve the purpose of this work, the researcher adopts the historical-critical approach to study the Psalms and a contextual approach to the interpretation of Psalm 23. The historical-critical approach reveals two schools of thought: first, that Psalm 23 is a prayer psalm that reflects the experience of a real individual, and second, that Psalm 23 reflects the experience of Israel as a community. It is therefore possible that the psalm evolved from an individual thanksgiving psalm to a communal hymn. However, in its canonical form, the psalm has been given various applications. Therefore, as a prayer psalm, it is the prayer of the psalmist for deliverance from a threat or an insecure situation. As a thanksgiving psalm, it summarizes the entire experience of the Israelites up to the time it was sung. This research reveals that theological motifs such as “shepherd,” “the valley of the shadow of death,” “rod and staff,” employed in the description of the relationship between the psalmist and Yahweh, as well as the psalmist’s personal experience, can be applied to solve the problem of security challenges in Nigeria. Thus, the “valley of the shadow of death” symbolizes the insecure situation, while “the shepherd” with his “rod and staff” describes the Nigerian leader and their responsibility in ensuring the security of life and property.

INTRODUCTION

The Psalms, to a great extent, contribute to a fuller understanding of the Old Testament in a number of ways. For instance, the various themes, traditions, persons, events, and values come together as a whole and are integrated and celebrated in a community context of prayer and worship; first at the various shrines throughout the entire Israelite nation and later in Solomon’s and Zerubbabel’s Temple (Ceresko 257). The Psalms are a form of summary and a distillation of the entire Old Testament in the context of prayer and worship.

The Psalms also provide insight into Israel's understanding of the nature and character of Yahweh, the God whom Israel worshipped. This is evident in the titles used in reference to Yahweh. Yahweh is presented as the creator, redeemer, shepherd, rock of refuge, light, shield, saviour, etc. The Psalms portray Yahweh as kind, loving, merciful, just, generous, forgiving, all-powerful, and strong. These are evident in the actions and events through which Yahweh touched the lives of these people, both as individuals and as a community (258).

Generally, the Psalter provides the most reliable theological, pastoral, and liturgical resources in the entire biblical tradition (Brueggemann 15). It is also of great importance in biblical scholarship because it is the Old Testament book that portrays most clearly the varied responses of human faith. Through the psalms, the spiritual insight and religious heritage of ancient Israel have had a profound and lasting impact on humanity; they express the whole range of human feeling and experience, from dark depression to exuberating joy; they are noted in particular circumstances, yet they are timeless. Thus, the Psalms are often the first point of call for Christians when going through various life experiences, as they see God through the eyes of the psalmists.

Psalms 23 is a 'Psalm of thanksgiving' (Brueggemann 154), popularly called the 'Shepherd's Psalm' (Brown 31). The psalmist asserts confidence in Yahweh's magnanimity and protection; using evocative metaphors such as shepherd, grassy meadows, still waters, path, dark valley, rod and staff, table, cup, and oil, the psalmist pictures one living in a serene environment with all one ever needs, irrespective of the threat of enemies (Brown 32). The dating of this psalm is estimated to be between the later life of David and sometime before the Exile. Most conservative scholars, who choose to adhere to tradition, consider Psalm 23 as a psalm written by an individual author, possibly David, as the title of the psalm implies, who expresses faith in Yahweh based on his experiences at that particular time (VanGemenen 823).

Psalms 23 is a psalm of comfort and assurance; it addresses the psychological and mental effects of insecurity and also gives the assurance of provision, guidance, restoration, and protection. It is against this background that this researcher seeks to interpret Psalm 23 to determine its relevance to Nigeria at this critical juncture in her history.

Nigeria is sitting on abundant "green pasture" similar to what is described in Psalm 23, but paradoxically, she is facing the challenge of economic stability. For a long time, Nigeria has occupied a very sensitive position in security matters among the committee of African nations because of the internal security the nation has enjoyed. However, today the case is not the same as Nigeria is beginning to struggle with her own internal security; there have been cases of insurgencies here and there, such as the various sects of Niger Delta Militants,

BokoHarram insurgency, Herdsmen marauders, kidnapping in many states, etc. which has led to the loss of life of thousand Nigerian citizens and many others left devastated and homeless. Consequently, today, an average Nigerian citizen is highly insecure; the fear of these menaces is so real that it cannot be denied. Also, Nigeria is facing the danger of disintegration and its people are losing fast the nationalistic spirit that has held it together for long. What more! Nigeria is losing its workforce to other nations due to migration to places of greener pasture as well as to seek refuge in those nations.

The above observations lead to the following posers: What is the relevance of Psalm 23 for contemporary Nigerian citizens? What is the cause of insecurity in Nigeria? Moreover, what is the interest of the various insurgents? Nigeria, like Israel, is blessed with abundant natural resources; this being the case, why is an average Nigerian not enjoying food security, and why is Nigeria still struggling with its economy? Why the high rate of unemployment? What is the cause of the youth restiveness? How can Nigerian citizens attain the state of ‘shalom’ described in Psalm 23 in the face of the current terrible fear of insecurity and disease? Therefore, in this research, we shall study Psalm 23 in its proper historical context and apply its meaning and implications to the problem of insecurity in Nigeria.

The researcher adopted the historical-critical method and contextual interpretation in the study. The former was used to study the Psalms and Psalm 23 in order to determine the nature of the text in the light of its total socio-cultural context and the background out of which it emerged. The latter was used in the interpretation and application of Psalm 23 to insecurity.

The Book of Psalms

The Hebrew Old Testament is divided into three main divisions: the law, the prophets, and the Writings. The Psalms belong to the Writings (Ketubim), a miscellaneous collection which includes the Wisdom Books, such as Job, Proverbs, and Ecclesiastes (Anderson 9). Traditionally, the Psalms is divided into five books each ending with a doxology, a formal ascription of praise to God: Book I: Psalms 1 – 41, Book II: Psalms 42 – 72, Book III: Psalms 73 – 89, Book IV: Psalms 90 – 106, and Book V: Psalms 107 – 150 (Harrington 285; Pat and David 359).

Psalm 150 serves as a doxology to the entire collection (Fohrer 293; Walter 754). According to Pat and David, Book I has mainly personal psalms, Books II and III mainly national psalms, and Books IV and V psalms for public worship. The psalms within each book are often grouped according to common themes, a common purpose, or a common author or collection (359). The division above is the last stage of a long and complicated course of development, modeled after the arrangement of the first five books of the Pentateuch, perhaps to help confer

canonical status on the Psalms, following the canonization of the Torah (Alter xix).

Scholars have attempted to classify the psalms by various criteria. For example, Herman Gunkel, a form critic, grouped them according to themes, literary types, or genres. There are psalms which plead with God and psalms which praise him; psalms which appeal for forgiveness, or the destruction of enemies; psalms of prayers for kings, or for the nation; 'wisdom' psalms such as Psalm 119 which celebrate the greatness of God's teaching (*Torah*), while many other psalms are a blend of several of these common themes. DeClaissé-Walford, in her book *Introduction to the Psalms: A Song from Ancient Israel*, following Gunkel's proposition, also identifies four major *Gattungen* of psalms in the Psalter (20-26). Therefore, the Psalter as we have it today has undergone many centuries of growth. They were individual psalms which existed separately until they were collected, edited, and arranged in the second century B.C.E.

Psalms Interpretation

Ademiluka reports extensively on the history of Psalm interpretation in his thesis "The Use of Psalms in African Context" (10-45), starting from the period before the development of the form-critical approach to the Old Testament, through the period of the form-critical approach, the theological approach, to the liturgical use of the Psalms. According to him, the earliest method of interpreting the Psalms before the development of the form-critical method was by means of the superscriptions, which are given to the majority of them. While some of these superscriptions are musical terms, others are associated with human names such as David, Korah, Asaph, Heman, Moses, and Solomon. It must be noted that the meaning of some of these superscriptions can only be guessed, albeit some early scholars sought to interpret the Psalms by means of these titles.

Another dimension to this early method of interpreting the psalms, according to Ademiluka, is an emphasis on the religious and poetic compositions of the psalms, which express individual piety. Thus, each psalm was considered the written proclamation of a poet. This approach studies the Psalms with a view to bringing out the piety and genius of the individual poets who sought to give expression to their inward feelings and emotional experiences so that others might learn from them. He reports further that after the method stated above, scholars turned to a purely historical approach. This approach seeks to place each psalm in its proper chronological place in the history of Israel. By implication, it dissects each psalm in an effort to reflect on the historical events, situation, and environment that occasioned it. Some scholars based their dating of the psalms on this approach (12 - 13).

Ademiluka reports yet another dimension to the interpretation of the Psalms; he states that Sigmund Mowinckel, followed by other scholars, builds on the work of

Gunkel. According to him, Mowinkel proposes a liturgical hypothesis for interpreting the Psalms, highlighting the similarities between ancient Near Eastern rituals and those of ancient Israel. These scholars associate the Psalms with different annual festivals of the Israelites. The similarities between ancient Near Eastern poetry and the Psalms have also led a group of form-critics to interpret the Psalms in the light of covenant theology. These scholars include W. Eichrodt, G. Von Rad, G. E. Mendenhall, and A. Weiser. To them, the Israelites adopted the entire ancient Near Eastern treaty scheme to express their belief in a covenant relationship to Yahweh. A. Weiser, according to Ademiluka, finds evidence within the Psalter to support this position (22).

Moreover, a theological approach was used in interpreting the Psalter. The theological approach seeks to bridge the gap between critical exegesis and the actual faith of the church. This approach was based on Karl Barth's concept of the inspiration of Scripture. Scholars who championed the use of a theological approach to Psalms study believe that the various psalm types were determined by divine occurrence, hence they attempt to show the relevance of each literary type to contemporary Christian worship. Ademiluka, citing Childs, one of the strong proponents of this view, states that "a Psalm or Psalm-type is capable of different interpretations for successive generations" (35). Ademiluka dedicates the rest of his work to discussing the distinctive way the psalm is used and applied in the African context.

Another outstanding work on the Psalms is the article of John Eaton titled "The Psalms in their Setting" (363-364) in the *Zondervan Handbook to the Bible*. In this essay, Eaton whimsically demonstrates how the Psalms function in the annual festival of ancient Israel. However, before this, Eaton notes that two perspectives have been fruitful in the modern study of the Psalms: inquiry into their original use and consideration of how the compilers of the final collection viewed them.

Walter Brueggemann, in his book *The Message of the Psalms: A Theological Commentary*, examines the liberal approach to psalm interpretation, comparing it with the theological approach. Brueggemann sets out by clarifying the concept of each of the approaches and notes that each of these approaches proceeds without much knowledge of attention to, or impact on, the other. He sees a weakness in the devotional tradition approach because it disregards the perspectives and insights of scholarship. On the other hand, he considers the scholarly tradition of interpretation frequently dry because it lingers excessively on formal questions, with an inability or reluctance to bring its insight and methods to substantive matters of exposition. Brueggemann submits that "what seems to be needed... is a *postcritical* interpretation that lets the devotional and scholarly traditions support, inform, and correct each other, so that the formal gains of scholarly methods may enhance and strengthen, as well as criticize, the substance of genuine piety in its handling of the Psalms" (15-16). Brueggemann's method permits interpreters to

enter the Psalms at whatever level they are able, in ways that are either primitive or sophisticated, limited or comprehensive. However, it does not give specific parameters that should guide an interpreter.

Also, David G. Firth, in his article “Psalms of Testimony,” argues for a transition from the traditional form-critical approach to a renewal of the old approach. What Firth implies by “old approach” is an approach that does not just consider the Psalter as a hymnbook but as the prayer book of the synagogue and, invariably, an instructional book.

From the foregoing, it is clear that Psalms interpretation has basically two dimensions: the early historical method or theological approach, which seeks to interpret the psalms from the angle of the devotional tradition of piety, and the form-critical approach, which is purely scholarly. However, Ademiluka’s work includes a third dimension to the interpretation of the Psalms, which is the African approach. However, none of the scholars reviewed above has applied psalm interpretation to the problem of insecurity.

Interpretations and Applications of Psalm 23

Text of Psalm 23

1. A Psalm of David. The LORD is my shepherd; I shall not want.	א מְנוּמֹר לְדוֹג יִהְיֶה רֹעִי לֹא אֶחְסָר:
2. He makes me to lie down in green pastures; He leads me beside the still waters.	ב בְּנֵאֲוֹת דְּשָׂא נִרְבִּיצָנִי עַל־מֵי מְנוּחֹת יְנַחֲמֵנִי:
3. He restores my soul; He leads me in the paths of righteousness For His name’s sake.	ג נִפְשִׁי יִשׁוּבֵב יְנַחֲמֵנִי כְּמַעְגְלֵי־צֶדֶק לְמַעַן שְׁמוֹ:
4. Yea, though I walk through the valley of the shadow of death, I will fear no evil; For You are with me; Your rod and Your staff, they comfort me.	ד גַּם כִּי־אֵלֶךְ בְּגִיא צַלְמוֹת לֹא־אִירָא רָע כִּי־אַתָּה עִמָּדִי שִׁבְטֶךָ וּמִשְׁעַנְיֶךָ הֵמָּה יְנַחֲמֵנִי:
5. You prepare a table before me in the presence of my enemies; You anoint my head with oil; My cup runs over.	ה תַּעֲרֶךְ לִפְנָיו שִׁלְחֹן נֶגֶד צָרָרִי דֹשְׁנָתָה בַּשֶּׁמֶן רֹאשִׁי כוֹסֵי רוּחָה:
6. Surely goodness and mercy shall follow me all the days of my life: and I will dwell in the house of the LORD forever (NKJV).	ו אֵדָו טוֹב וְחַסֵּד יִרְדְּפוּנִי כָּל־יְמֵי חַיִּי וְשָׁבְתִי בְּבֵית־יְהוָה לְאָרְךָ יָמִים:

William Brown, using the tools of literary studies, in his book *Interpreting Biblical Texts: Psalms*, analyzes the different genres found in the Psalms. Brown

classifies Psalms 23 and 42:1-8 as metaphoric poetry. He states that “a metaphor enables the reader to see something new about the target domain and thereby gain new insight about the metaphor’s object” (30). Also, he states that “a metaphor’s contribution to the construction of meaning is more suggestive than limiting.... Through metaphor, poetry generates a surplus of semantic connections...” (31). This background knowledge of metaphor helps to conceive an interpretation of Psalm 23 that is beyond the immediate situation of the writer.

Although Brown emphasizes that the metaphorical feature of Psalm 23 could give it a more profound meaning beyond its traditional interpretation, his commentary on the Psalm follows the same traditional interpretation. Using the imagery and metaphors of Psalm 23, he demonstrates how the “shepherd” is identified as “YHWH God,” as found in other ancient Near Eastern literatures. He examines the implications of God’s rule, his care for the sheep, and his protective role. According to him, in verse 5, the scene shifted from the pastoral to the domestic; God is no longer a shepherd, but a gracious host.

Similarly, James L Crenshaw, in his book, *The Psalms: An Introduction*, classifies Psalm 23 under prayer psalms. Moreover, like Brown above, he follows the traditional interpretation in his commentary. According to him, the emphasis falls initially on the divine shepherd but gives way to the image of a host. Crenshaw interprets Psalm 23 within the context of the divine protection enjoyed by those who make Yahweh their God, whether as an individual or a community. In the same vein, WillienVanGemeren, in his commentary on the “Psalms” in *The Expositor’s Bible Commentary on the Old Testament*, reads Psalm 23 as a psalm of “trust and confidence,” because it expresses confidence in God’s goodness in this life and in the life to come. According to him, the personal way in which the psalmist speaks of God, the images of God’s soothing guidance, and the ensuing confidence in God are factors that make this psalm charming and beloved. VanGemeren’s commentary follows the usual traditional interpretation of Psalm 23; he did not take into consideration the implications of the psalm for Israel as a community bonded to Yahweh in covenant.

Kyle M. Yates (503–504), who simply structures the psalm into two parts (“God as the Personal Shepherd and God as the Gracious Host”), states that the strong affirmation of faith in Psalm 23 drives away grief, sadness, and doubt and brings peace, contentment, and trust to those who share the psalmist’s sublimed confidence. According to Yates, behind the first sentence, “the Lord is my shepherd,” lies a long experience of trusting God. Additionally, the rich corporate relationship of Israel with God is appropriated as an individual realization. On God as the gracious host, Yates views the psalmist as the guest of honour at God’s house, enjoying the protection and warm hospitality of God. According to Yates,

the greatest blessing of the psalmist will be an intimate fellowship with God through continual worship of Him.

Sigmund Mowinkel discusses the *gattungen* of Psalm 23 in his book, *The Psalms in Israel's Worship*, translated by Ap-Thomas. He contemplates that psalm 23 could either be classified under psalms of confident prayer or psalm of thanksgiving. To him, the psalmist pours eulogy on Yahweh for the aspects of his being and for his works past and present on which the psalmist builds his confidence and faith. After discussing the connection between a hymn of praise and prayer psalms, Mowinkel states that Psalm 23 is really meant to be a 'protective psalm' in danger or a thanksgiving psalm after the experience of salvation. He remarks, "... what gives it [Psalm 23] a priceless value to all ages may be the very fact that it stands there as a pure expression of confidence in God, unhindered by all special historical circumstances, an adequate expression of confidence of faith of all sorts of people, and at all times." On the final analysis, he submits that the psalm is an expression of the religious traditions of the people of the covenant, and an expression of the conception of God with which they were entrusted, and of the personal experience of God in their own lives and the attitude to life created by these.

According to Waltke and Houston, the Early Church Fathers, such as St. Augustine, Athanasius (c. 296 - 373), Cyril of Alexander (c. 370 - 444), Theodore of Cyrrhus (c. 393 - 457), interpret Psalm 23 in reference to baptism, Eucharist, and persecution. This implies that Psalm 23 may have acquired importance as a baptismal hymn by this period. Furthermore, the authors inform that Geroch of Reichersberg (c. 1093 - 1169) did a scholarly commentary on Psalm 23, according to which "The Lord is my Shepherd because he created me and gave me life." Geroch interprets the "pastures" to be the "scriptures", where he (Geroch) was established as a catechumen. The "leading" is the "*educante*." For Geroch, the psalm essentially describes the effect of the grace of God upon the life of the Christian so that at the end of life, there will be no fear of death. He allegorizes "thy rod" as light discipline for the child of God, and the "staff" as heavy discipline necessary to knock down the pride of the sinner (418).

Moreover, Waltke and Houston report that the Fifteenth-Century reformers use a more scholarly approach in their commentary on Psalm 23, stating that Nicholas of Lyra (c. 1270 - 1349) interprets the psalm in reference to its *Sit imLeben*. Following Rashi a Hebrew scholar, Nicholas does not refer to the Eucharistic meal; instead he refers to I Samuel 22 and submits that "this psalm can be explained morally, concerning a devout man fleeing from the world, as if from a place of perils, and finding refuge in a place of religion; trusting in divine provision and defense from adversaries not only of the body but also of the mind." According to Walke and Houston, Denys the Carthusian (c. 1270 - 1349)

views the psalm as one of gratitude for being given sound doctrine and for receiving the sacrament of baptism, as well as being given spiritual direction. He adds an original anagogical interpretation of Psalm 23. According to him, the benefit of the celebration of this psalm is in the heavenly or eternal state, when the saints will be “ruled” eternally, wanting nothing. The authors report that Jacques Lefèvre d’Étaples (c. 1455 - 1536) and Martin Luther (c. 1483 - 1546) gave the psalm a Christological interpretation.

Another fascinating interpretation is that of Philip Melanchthon (c. 1497 - 1560), who in his commentary applied Psalm 23 to the situation of the nation. According to Waltke and Houston, when Melanchthon was composing his commentary, the Turks advanced to the doors of Vienna, threatening war and a complete devastation of all Europe and of the universal church of Christ, so he includes a reference to them. He calls for prayer, saying, “let us ask from God that he may protect and defend us against these [such] great dangers, lest knowledge of him be destroyed” (422). Melanchthon views Psalm 23 as a completely impersonal psalm of prayer with national implications.

John Calvin (1509–1564) comments on the “shepherd,” viewing it as a persisting metaphor used to describe Christ’s benefit for his followers. He believes the psalm is a psalm of thanksgiving. According to him, the “sheep” represents God’s people, because wandering about is the characteristic of God’s people, which is the consequence of their wayward sinfulness and “the hiddenness of God”. The “rod” is to bridle the wantonness of the flesh and spur us to thanksgiving and godliness. Calvin believes that “I will be afraid of no harm” is possible because of the protection provided by the shepherd’s staff, and that “prepare a table” is a literal provision made by any good father. For Calvin, Psalm 23 is summed up in the words of Psalm 33:12 “Blessed are the people whose God is the Lord” (Waltke and Houston 429-431).

According to Waltke and Houston, after Calvin, the Psalms were popularized; they were versified and set into melodies, and were sung congregationally. In the authors’ own commentary, they assert that Psalm 23 is a song of Trust in I AM. For them, Psalm 23 describes the benefit an individual, “a sheep,” derives from a relationship with God the “shepherd,” which includes provision, restoration, and protection. They submit that the “shepherd” is Jesus Christ, while the “sheep” are Christians. He guides, provides, and protects his sheep through the Holy Spirit, the Scriptures, the holy church, and the holy sacraments. They also suggest that Christ, the chief shepherd, also appoints church leaders as sub-shepherds to equip the Christian for the work of service.

Williams L Holladay, in an epilogue to his book, *The Psalms through Three Thousand Years: Prayer Book of Witnesses*, discusses the history of the interpretation and application of Psalm 23 in America in what he titles “How the

Twenty-third Psalm Became an American Secular Icon.” According to him, the psalm was initially written in public school prayer books to be recited daily by each pupil. He states that the words of Jesus in John 10, in which he identifies himself as the Good Shepherd, reinforced the use of the psalm in America. He adds that the psalm was added to the service for the burial of the dead only in the 1979 revision, when the Methodist Church offered a delicate balance between fear and hope; the ceremony shifted radically towards hope.

According to Holladay, the appropriation of Psalm 23 by American circular culture occurred two decades after the Civil War (362). He informs that Henry Ward Beecher (1813 - 1887), a popular American preacher, gave tribute to Psalm 23 in his lecture on the way in which the scripture reflects the “sacred joy of souls in trial.” On the relevance of the psalm, Holladay cites Beecher thus:

It has poured balm and consolation into the hearts of the sick, captives in dungeons, widows in their pinching grief, and orphans in their loneliness. Dying soldiers have died more easily as it was read to them; ghastly hospitals have been illuminated; it has visited the prisoner and broken his chains, and, like Peter’s angel, led him forth in imagination, and sung him back to his home again. It has made the dying enslaved Christian freer than his master, and consoled those whom, dying, he left behind mourning, not so much that he was gone as because they were left behind, and could not go too (363).

The summary of Holladay’s position on Psalm 23 is as follows:

The psalm could be appropriated for a rite of passage, since it appears to move from references to life (“He leadeth me beside the still waters”) to death (“yea, though I walk through the valley of the shadow of death, I will fear no evil, for thou art with me”) to eternal life (“and I shall dwell in the house of the Lord for ever [forever]”). It is a psalm that could be used in public contexts, acceptable to both Jews and Christians, and giving no offense to anyone (364).

It suffices here to say that no psalm has attracted much attention and comment like Psalm 23; though short and simple, it can be applied to many life situations. However, apart from Melanchthon’s commentary, none of the scholars reviewed above applied the interpretation of the Psalm to the problem of insecurity or conceived it to have any national implication. However, Melanchthon makes his reference only in parsing, hence the need for more detailed research on Psalm 23 in the light of its national relevance and implications for insecurity challenges.

Implications of Psalm 23 for Human Insecurity in Nigeria

Insecurity as “Shadow of Death”

The subject of insecurity is more popular in contemporary society than it was in the past. This state of being unsafe or insecure was the same situation expressed by the psalmist in Psalm 23:4, where he/she states, “Yea, though I walk through the valley of the shadow of death....” The “shadow of death” as used in this text does not imply that it is a mere shadow, but rather it is a Hebrew idiom for the darkest darkness or a life-threatening or near-death situation. Hence, “the valley of the shadow of death” refers to a position surrounded by great perils. In the same way, the sheep are exposed to pitfalls and devouring beasts in the blackest darkness when they are returning home late. A. S. Brooke illustrates this imagery better by relating it to David’s experience while fleeing from Absalom. According to him,

“The valley,” or ravine, “of the shadow of death,” or, as it may be translated, “of deep shades,” can, without any fancifulness, be connected with the scenery through which he [David] passed in his flight. He must, after crossing Olivet, have descended to the fords of the Jordan by one of the rocky passes which lead from the tableland of Jerusalem. These deep ravines were full of ghastly shadows, and David passed down one of them as the evening began to fall and waited by the ford of the Jordan until midnight. It is not improbable that we have here the source of the image in this verse. Such a march must have left a strong impression on his imagination. The weird and fierce character of the desolate ravine, the long and deathly shadows which chilled him as the sun sank, the fierce curses of Shimei, the fear behind him, the agony in his own heart, repeating the impression of the landscape, fastened the image of it in his memory forever (458-459).

Therefore, the “shadow or shade of death” aptly describes the contemporary Nigerian context. One of the indices of insecurity in Nigeria is kidnapping; a kidnapped individual in the hands of the kidnappers is first threatened with a gun, thereby compelled to comply. He/she is then blindfolded and taken to a creek, forest, bush, desert, or an unfinished building in a strange location. The victim is then starved and subjected to an inhuman situation, not knowing what evil might befall him/her. Such a situation is a “shadow of death” experience for the kidnapped person.

For the psalmist, the “shadow of death” implies the perilous moments in his life when he feared death. Similarly, “shadow of death” occurs in different forms in Nigeria. Public places such as religious centres, shopping complexes, markets, garages, etc, are fast becoming places of “shadow of death” as a result of the *Boko Haram* insurgency. Women in *hijab* face potential dangers (“Shadows of death”)

because women members of the Boko Haram sect are now armed with bombs to cause explosions in public places. Their men would attack villages and shoot at people and buildings sporadically until the whole place is leveled. They would capture those who attempt to escape and slaughter them one after the other. A Nigerian who goes through these experiences and comes out alive has gone through the “valley of the shadow of death” like the psalmist. Also, herder insurgents now lurk around in hideouts, which are routes for local farmers. Many times, they have attacked farmers and killed them gruesomely. Thus, most places in Nigeria today are fast becoming “the valley of the shadow of death” to people living in them owing to incessant security threats.

The spate of other security challenges in Nigeria today subjects the populace to fear of death or the evils of other kinds daily. People live a life of uncertainty; any hour can bring disaster, danger, and distress from unknown quarters. Life is full of hazards, and no one can tell what a day will produce in terms of trouble. Therefore, Nigerians need to be security-conscious and alert when going through “dangerous” places in Nigeria.

Nigerian Leaders as “Shepherd”

As reported earlier, modern literary approaches to psalm study indicate that Psalm 23 is part of the corpus of individual thanksgiving psalms. However, it also possesses one of the characteristics of individual or communal lament. Its setting is on a pastoral domain with great emphasis on the divine shepherd. However, within the framework of this research, the shepherd metaphor will be interpreted as temporal leaders.

A good shepherd is gentle, kind, intelligent, brave, and selfless in his devotion to his flock. When sheep starve, struggle, suffer endless hardship, and are killed, it is an indication that they are under a bad shepherd. Accordingly, the nature of Nigeria’s security challenge does not call for a gentle approach; instead, it calls for a bold and intelligent one. Therefore, Nigeria needs a leader in that capacity. Nigerian leaders like the divine shepherd in verse 4c of Psalm 23 (“... thy rod and thy staff they comfort me.”) are to use their “rod and staff” effectively to correct and defend the citizenry. The metaphor of “rod and staff” denotes an instrument of correction and equipment for defence. In the Nigerian context, they signify the security forces and law enforcement agencies, which are instruments of correction and defence in the hands of the Nigerian leaders.

The shepherd ensures adequate security for his sheep by taking every necessary security measure. The comfort and confidence of the sheep are predicated on this, so that even when they walk through the valley of the shadow of death (security threats), they fear no evil. This metaphor also refers to the government's responsibility in equipping the security forces and the judicial system to combat terrorism in Nigeria. Moreover, sheep are defenseless; their defense depends

mainly on the strength of their shepherd. They are helpless, timid, and feeble creatures with little or no means of self-defence, except to run. The same case applies to humans; our first impulse is to get up and run. However, nothing so quiets and reassures the sheep like seeing their shepherd in the field during times of terror. They are comforted and consoled in seeing the rod and staff in the shepherd's skilful hands.

Security of life and property represents perhaps the most fundamental duty of any government. The 1999 Constitution of Nigeria states that "The security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of Government" (Section 14 (2) (b)). Security is the foundation on which the success of all initiatives of the government in ensuring good governance is anchored. However, it has presented the most significant challenge to governments all over the world, as well as Nigeria. The Nigerian security forces contain several contradictions, incongruities, and internal disjunctions that have weakened their strength in the face of contemporary security challenges. At some point, most especially during Goodluck Jonathan's administration, they became less reliable to the point that people felt unsafe. For example, the Nigerian military which is the largest, most capable military in West Africa with major foreign deployments under ECOWAS and the AU, as well as extensive UN PKO (Peace Keeping Operation) commitments since independence in 1960 (*Globalsecurity.org*), in recent time has become weak due to low morale among its troops to the point that there were cases of deserters. This was possibly orchestrated by the challenges they faced on the war front, where the terrorist gangs were more powerfully armed than they were. Next, we discuss some of the challenges faced in the drive towards an efficient service delivery by security operatives in Nigeria.

Studies have identified widespread corruption as the leading cause of poor performance among most of Nigeria's security operatives, particularly the military and police. Although corruption is a national malady, it is more prevalent among security and law enforcement personnel. The worst of this malaise manifests in the Ministry of Defence. For instance, in 2014, security swallowed nearly 938 billion naira (\$5.8 billion), a quarter of the federal budget. Out of that, the defense ministry took more than a third, but only 10 percent was for capital spending, while the senior officers pocketed the rest of the money (*Globalsecurity.org*). There have also been several scandals surrounding the so-called security votes, which allow politicians to appropriate millions of dollars behind closed doors simply by evoking national security. As a result, funds intended to purchase equipment and pay salaries go missing, leaving the military poorly equipped and demoralized. More recently, the Army has been plagued by allegations that officers are routinely bribed by the *Boko Haram* sect so much that they coordinate attacks, not only for direct private gain but also to justify the 20

percent of the national budget that Nigeria allocates to the armed forces to fight terrorism (*saharareporters.com*).

Since corruption is one of the factors maligning Nigeria's security system, it therefore behooves the government to develop, communicate, and implement a concrete plan to curb it. The defense sector should be scrutinized and placed under close check. The ministry should be required to publish the defense budget and account for massive off-budget defense expenditure, including federal funds, revenue from peacekeeping, and foreign aid. The Office of the Auditor-General should be allowed access to accounts of the intelligence services and other secret programs. Moreover, as Uwimana and Wawro opine, the Nigerian defense and security forces should also focus on training their personnel on how to tackle corruption, giving them practical guidance to navigate this complicated moral and logistical issue. To support personnel who expose corruption, existing whistleblower protection laws must be enforced (*www.saharareporters.com*). Leaders who support the fight against terrorism must also use the powers they have within their own borders to tackle corruption.

They must implement sanctions and visa bans on the corrupt. They must utilize their investigative capacity and prosecution powers to uncover corruption, and enforce anti-money laundering regulations. Once the issue of corruption is addressed, it will become tough for terrorist groups to operate freely; as such, there will be a decline in terrorism, proper appropriation of funds to remunerate and equip the security outfits, and effective security services delivery, which will accordingly enhance the security of lives and properties in Nigeria.

Physical infrastructure and equipment are often a primary obstacle to a successful security system in any given society. Many years of inadequate investment in equipment or inappropriate investment in security infrastructure in Nigeria leave law enforcement agencies with uninhabitable accommodation, archaic and unserviceable equipment, and obsolete communication gadgets, among other issues. The absence of an institutional framework and a standardized method of data collection for crime information management has significantly impacted the ability of law enforcement agencies to produce reliable official statistics on crime (Otubu 1-16).

For the security unit to be effective, it must be equipped with fast-moving vehicles installed with a nationwide VHF (Very High Frequency) radio system for inter- and intra-agency communication. This will enhance coordinated response to terrorism/insurgency in Nigeria. Nigeria's National Intelligence Agency (NIA), the State Security Service (SSS), the Directorate of Military Intelligence (DMI), the Police, Customs, and Immigration, among others, must work together to overcome inter-agency rivalry and achieve the common good. There is a need for active and seamless information sharing and harnessing of the capabilities of the

various security agencies. They must also be equipped with standard APCs (Armored Personnel Carriers), warships, helicopters, scientific crime prevention facilities, and other modern, sophisticated weapons to combat high-scale crimes. The detection and prevention of crimes and the enforcement of laws designed to protect national security can only be effective or efficient where adequate security infrastructure exists (Otubu 1-16). A well-organized, strong, and efficient security force present in strategic locations in all the geo-political zones in Nigeria will not only reduce terrorism but it will also boost the confidence and hope of Nigerians and foreigners in the government and its capacity to defend them.

CONCLUSION

The research reveals how the Psalms, including Psalm 23, evolved from an individual thanksgiving psalm to a communal hymn. However, Psalm 23 in its canonical form has been given various applications. As a prayer psalm, it is the prayer of the psalmist for deliverance from a threat or an insecure situation. As a thanksgiving psalm, it summarizes the entire experience of the Israelites up to the time it was sung.

Theological motifs, such as “the valley of the shadow of death,” “shepherd,” “sheep,” and other metaphors in Psalm 23, are applicable in addressing the security challenges in Nigeria. Identifying elements of security threats, such as public places, religious centers, isolated villages, farms, and footpaths in remote places, women in hijab, etc., as shadows of death should create enough alertness and encourage individual Nigerians to take caution and possible defensive measures against security threats. Accordingly, Nigerian leaders who are the shepherds, knowing fully well that the security of lives and properties is one of their primary responsibilities, need to maintain and equip the states’ security apparatus to tackle security threats effectively.

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